

SYSTEM OF PREPARING FUTURE TEACHERS FOR PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY ON THE SOCIALIZATION OF STUDENTS ON THE BASE OF GENDER APPROACH

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Abstract: This article contains opinions about the scientific-theoretical basis of preparing students for professional activities aimed at socializing youth based on gender approach.

Key words: Educational system, methodology, gender approach, professional activity, pedagogue, cognitive-informational, individual.

Since behavior is an external expression of the inner world of a person and the entire system of his life relationships, values, ideals, we identified the third component of the gender-role behavior style - the behavior component. Highlighting this component, as well as solving the problem related to the education of the student's readiness to define and solve the problems of professional activity, in accordance with the normative image of the "second" gender equality and the student's personality as the "intellectual potential of the country" in the practice of higher education was related to the necessity. The organization of such capabilities of the individual includes not only the mental activity itself, but also the formation and development of the individual who experiences the need for "sacrifice" in various types of professional activities as a significantly important link.

We emphasized that we connect the activity of a higher education student to the factors of gender socialization of an individual. According to the theory of A. S. Belkin, vital (vitagen) experience is important - information that has become the property of a person (thoughts, feelings, actions lived by a person). A student of higher education has the task of educating and constantly improving the ability to work independently in accordance with experience, understanding the interdependence of individual and collective activities in the context of the dynamic development of culture¹. Active interaction with the surrounding reality, during which a person acts as a subject with a purposeful effect on the objects of the surrounding world, is called activity. According to V. S. Lednev, one aspect of higher education is to improve the personal characteristics of a higher education student².

Analysis of the activity structure shows that the main elements of its content are:

- motives that encourage activity;
- goals - results aimed at achieving activity;
- the means by which the activity is carried out.

¹ Формирование учебной деятельности студентов [Текст] / под ред. В.Я.Ляудиса. - М.: Изд-во Моск. ун-та, 1989. - 240 с.

² Леднев, В.С. Содержание образования [Текст]: учеб. пособие / В.С. Леднев. - М.: Высш. шк., 1989. - 360 с.

Activity includes internal, ideal actions that are performed mentally and provide a person with comprehensive direction in the surrounding world. According to teachers, activity creates conditions for self-knowledge, self-development and self-realization of a person in the system of social relations. According to A. N. Leontiev's hypothesis about the leading type of activity developed in the works of D. B. Elkonin, V. V. Davydov and others, the activity determines the emergence and formation of the main psychological neoplasms of a person at this stage of the development of the individual. It is called a leader. A change in leading activity is associated with the emergence of new needs and motives, which determines a change in the system of a person's relationships with other people (the state of a person)³.

Based on the above, all three components of the gender behavior style of a higher education student personality (cognitive-informational, reflective and behavioral) that we have highlighted are closely related and interconnected. As we noted above, the important features of the gender behavior style are not only related to the formation of motivation, value orientations and reflection mechanisms, but also to the subjective experience gained while performing a certain gender role.

Based on the above, on the basis of the behavioral component, we consider the experience of gender behavior of a person in fulfilling civic, family and professional roles of a higher education student. According to specific styles of gender behavior, personal experience is associated with the superiority of social relations in the traditional performance of roles, the superiority of individual characteristics in accordance with the "second" gender, as well as the equality of the "second" gender with subcultural norms and values possible Indicators of the behavioral component: the direction of activity (operational, analytical, systematic modeling activities), the level of "reflected subjectivity" (individual, individually relevant, supra-individual) and communication style (directive or supportive empowering, individual and personal).

The direction of activity is related to the stable motives that direct the activity and behavior of a person. We call the recommended operational skills of activities and behaviors based on gender schemes, unconscious acceptance of norms, operational (template) activities. This type of activity can describe a higher education student who, as we mentioned above, fulfills traditional gender roles according to a personal "pattern" that reflects the views of everyday consciousness. In this case, the student of "intellectual potential" develops an internal role conflict with ambiguity in choosing a specific gender role.

As an intellectual capacity, the student is characterized by analytical activity, characterized by the ability to behave on the basis of the analysis of his experience. He has the ability to develop a rational system of gender behavior in accordance with the normative style by carrying out systematic modeling activities. Consciously planning the development of a personal style of gender behavior will help him to fulfill civic, family and professional roles.

A person's ability to strategically organize his activities, set and adjust goals, be aware of motives, build actions independently and evaluate their compliance with the planned, and make life plans is called subjectivity. Perception, knowledge, understanding of the interaction

³ Педагогический энциклопедический словарь [Текст] / под ред. Б.М.Бим-Бады. - М.: Большая Российская энциклопедия, 2003. - 528 с.: ил.

partner and oneself in interaction with him is called reflection. In interaction, reflection is a feedback mechanism that shows the consequences of the actions of both parties.

Thus, according to the theory of V. A. Petrovsky, we identified three levels of the formation of "reflected subjectivity": individual (changes in the effectiveness of one subject in contact with another), individual significance (identification of the individual as an ideal significant other reflection - "I and the other in me") and above the individual (identification of the subject, which includes the destruction of the ideological form, convergence - the formation of "we")⁴.

Based on the above, the student develops the skills of individual and non-individual reflection that contribute to the establishment of relationships based on the equality of the "second" gender and the normative image of the person. The human need to establish, maintain and improve relationships with people is called partnership. A person with this need not only constantly seeks people and is satisfied with emotionally positive communication with them, but also develops a rational system of gender behavior in accordance with the status of the person.

Communication is a complex and multifaceted process of interaction between people and their joint activities, which provides all the diversity of human life and relationships. In communication, the perception, understanding and evaluation of a person by a person belonging to certain socio-cultural types (masculine, feminine or androgynous) takes place. Communication is one of the human activities.

Due to the distinction of three aspects of communication: communicative, perceptive and interactive, we distinguished the communication style as one of the indicators of the behavioral component of the gendered behavior style: directive or supportive (exchange of information), individual (organization of interaction), personal (the process of establishing mutual understanding and mutual understanding).

According to G. M. Andreeva, in real communication practice, these parties do not exist in isolation⁵. Since communication performs normative, cognitive, emotional and actualizing functions, we performed these functions during the research work in the education of the gender-individual and gender-personal behavior style of the student.

Communication style is the totality of individual characteristics of a person, his methods and nature of interaction. According to gender psychology, the forms of interaction with partners of the same and opposite sex (verbal and non-verbal behavior) are manifestations of a directive style, pressure on the partner and usually "hand are divided into those defined by the term "support". Directive forms include correctness, restriction, introduction of sentences, repetition, interruption of speech. "Support" includes asking questions, feeling, repeating your words or the speaker's words, doubt and rejection, understanding, friendliness, intuition, smiling, laughing. Therefore, the directive or supportive communication style is considered by us to be a traditional form of communication. A student with a traditional style does not act actively in communication or acts passively when

⁴ Петровский, В.А. Личность в психологии: парадигма субъектности [Текст] / В.А.Петровский. - Ростов н /Дону, 1996. - 512 с.

⁵ Андреева, Г.М. Социальная психология [Текст]: учеб. для вузов/ Г.М.Андреева. - М.: Аспект Пресс, 2001. - 378 с.

discussing a problem, silently follows his own opinion. In the continuation of communication, a student with a supportive communication style tries to agree with the speaker, even if he does not agree with him internally.

Personal communication style is distinguished by us on the basis of individual characteristics of personality according to gender characteristics. A characteristic feature of this style is the ability of a person to use the strategies of the previous two communication styles and is not afraid of external comments. The development of a personal communication style allows the student to establish competent communication with communication partners, to "reveal himself in others", to act for him as a person, to allow others to perceive and evaluate his personality and activities actively, correctly, allows for a tactical, intelligent effect.

Thus, the reproductive-stereotypical style of the student's gender behavior implies the presence of an operational direction of activity, an individual level of "reflected subjectivity", a directive or supportive communication style. The gender-individual style is characterized by an analytical direction of activity, an individual significance level of "reflected subjectivity" and an individual style of communication. The gender-personal style of behavior is characterized by the direction of systematic modeling of personal activity, the level of "reflected subjectivity" above the individual level, and the style of personal communication. The level of existing indicators of gender-individual and gender-personal behavior style is related to the conditionality of the behavioral component with the cognitive-informational and reflective components, as we mentioned above.

Contributing to the development and education of students' independent activity skills, we carried out joint activities based on the organization of educational situations at all stages of experimental work. Educational situation is an organized system of variable components of the educational process, its psychological core is the teacher's interaction, relationship and communication with students and students. To determine the structure of the educational situation, we faced the following tasks:

- organizing the content of the educational process in accordance with the gender characteristics of students (developing a program of cognitive activities and mastered activities);
- transition from one level to another in the process of mastering a certain type of activity;
- to determine the content of the system of interactions and relations between students;
- development of a program for educating students' gender-individual and gender-personal style of personal behavior;
- analysis of the dynamics of interdependence of all the indicated components during experimental research work with students.

Above, we noted that in the process of gender socialization, young men and women can identify themselves with ideal images and with a certain important person and not critically accept their views, attitudes, and relationships. In experimental work, the teacher is one of the personal "examples" of activities and behavior for students. In the process of interpersonal interaction, young men and women introduced themselves to the group in which the activity was carried out, as well as to the reference person (boy or girl) who acts as a model at a certain stage of the research. During experimental work, students are able to exercise conscious control over their own behavior, carry out an internal dialogue in which

certain values and personal "patterns" (reflection) should be considered, evaluated, accepted or rejected. were ready.

We emphasized that the organization of the natural and cultural process of teaching and educating the personality of a higher education student includes three ways of joint activity of the teacher and the student: male, female and androgynous. The task of our research does not include the change of the "second" gender of boys and girls, our task was the task: the experience of activity and behavior in accordance with the equality of the "second" gender and the normative image of a student of higher education indicate the necessary methods of updating. Accordingly, based on the results of diagnostic methods, we created personalized characteristics and developed an activity program according to the individual gender characteristics of each student's personality.

In the first paragraph of this chapter, we described teaching methods that take into account the gender composition of the student audience. The "second" gender of the interaction participants was also taken into account in the implementation of independent and joint activities of teachers and students. We offered a traditional speech with a message or lecture to students with masculine qualities. In this type of activity, students focused on their experience, that is, on their ability to perceive the material as a whole and connect it with reality. Such students had no difficulty in giving examples from their own life practice.

For students with masculine qualities, we offered to organize discussions and methodical meetings in connection with their success in team activities. These students were engaged in the preparation of creative reports (related to the need for figurative thinking and self-awareness). Students creatively compiled creative reports about the work done in their circle classes in the form of posters, pictures, funny diagrams, caricatures, which was related to the belonging of this group of students to visualists. In the circle group, students with masculine characteristics were active in creating the image of a female hostess, leader, modern and business woman.

It should be noted that the tendency of creative nature has become relevant even in students with androgynous characteristics. As a rule, most of the time, male personalities acted as leaders, while androgynous people preferred conciliatory behavior. Students with androgynous personality traits could act as assistants in the implementation of a certain activity scenario without feeling submissive and dependent. The success of students with masculine personality traits in team activities made it possible to observe the manifestation of their "reflected subjectivity".

Taking into account the characteristics of students with feminine characteristics, we organized improvisation workshops for this category of students in connection with the importance of the semantic aspect of speech. These students participated little in discussions because they prefer to listen more than speak when it is necessary to demonstrate knowledge on a particular question or issue. Due to their preference for solitary activities focused on their inner subjective world and prone to introspection, they actively demonstrated their ability to express themselves and know themselves more deeply in educational activities. Interactions with students of this category showed that in interpersonal relationships, students show such qualities as modesty, shyness, uncertainty, tendency to perform other people's tasks, dependence on other people's opinion.

In interaction situations, female students acted more often as performers than as skilled organizers. It should be noted that the manifestation of students' activity was influenced by

their previously acquired personal status in the group. The positive emotional reaction of the participants of the third stage of the research helped to organize more conscious work on the development of a specific style of competent gender behavior. Each student could choose one of the circle's work areas and exercise their abilities in an activity that was interesting to them. Students with feminine characteristics initially felt tight, insecure, but with the help of the teacher and other participants of the research, they were able to overcome the obstacles in communication and joint activities.

We had to organize joint activities in such a way that every student, regardless of the "second" gender, would show his abilities in any activity. The desire of students to master the gender-personal style of behavior opens up prospects for the success of any type of activity, the professional performance of the entire spectrum of social (and in their composition, gender) roles.

The explanatory procedure helped to transfer the knowledge activity of each student to a new level of activity, served to develop scientific knowledge about gender socialization and individual knowledge and the ability to apply them in practice. Based on this, the sequence of mastering the actions of creating a written scientific statement served as the basis for the organization of scientific and research activities of students and self-improvement in their interactions in accordance with their personal experience.

As a result of working together, students developed an interest in research work, putting forward and justifying hypotheses on the problem of gender socialization, and developed scientific explanation skills. In this type of activity, the student not only implemented the recommended operational skills, but also developed skills based on the analysis of his experience. Thus, the direction of student activity has changed. Working with the logical structure of the text helped to develop the student's oral speech, which is an integral part of the student's communication style with the teacher and in their interaction with the teacher. The initial listening and discussion of the reports was carried out in one of the sessions of the scientific-pedagogical circle. Students participated in the discussion with interest, asked the speaker questions and expressed their opinions about the received information.

In training students' collaborative skills, we focused on how students approach the speaker and what methods the speaker uses to communicate. As we mentioned in the previous paragraph, this is correctness, restraint, suggestions, repetition (activity style). Or emotionality, questions, repetition of words, doubt and rejection, understanding, friendliness, intuitiveness, smile, laughter (supportive style). Discussion of the finished text of the report made it possible to compare different perspectives of the students both in understanding the problem and in choosing the methods of its interpretation. Students developed the ability to relate positions and arguments, to see different approaches to problem analysis, which contributed to the development of "reflective subjectivity". The student saw the solution of the problem not as a way of praise and encouragement, not as a means of satisfying their educational interests, but as a way of communication and establishing friendly relations with colleagues. Later, in the process of personal counseling, communication and communication style of the communication participants was changed. As a result of the discussion of the lectures, each speaker took into account the mistakes made during the preparation and managed to correct them. This form of work helped to develop competent communication skills, to treat each other with respect, and the ability to listen to the opinions of colleagues. In

the process of preparing for the speech, students focused on consciously planning the development of a personal style of gender behavior.

Summary

Currently, the problem of gender socialization of a person is related to the change in the stratification of society and the orientation of education policy to "ensure stable and dynamic development of a society with a high standard of living, civic, professional and household culture."

Turning the higher education system into a social institution responsible for preserving and increasing the "intellectual potential of the country", if the need for personalization based on the parity of the person's gender and "personal model" is satisfied, life, creativity, cooperation, family-oriented, mutual respect, professionalism.

A student of higher education, as a representative of the status group "intellectual potential of the country", strives to fully identify and develop the socially significant personal characteristics of an intellectual, personal abilities, gnostic and projective skills and competencies, civic, family and professional roles. it is distinguished by the need to realize its gender potential.

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